

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of Cadmium(II) Complexes with *N*-Salicylidene- and *N*-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amino Acids

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A new series of six-coordinated complexes of Cd^{II} with *N*-salicylidene- and *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amino acids has been prepared. Spectroscopic investigations have shown that ligands are coordinated to the metal ions in a terdentate manner with O,N,O donor site. Metal ions function as a trap for Schiff base intermediates, which facilitate the formation and isolation of metal derivatives.

Schiff bases are important class of ligands having many applications¹. They possess various biological activities² and have interesting structural problems³.

It was, therefore, thought of interest to prepare and characterise Cd^{II} complexes *in situ* with *N*-salicylidene- (sal) and *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene) (OHN) amino acids (amino acids = glycine, L-alanine, L-phenylalanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-histidine and L-tryptophan).

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analyses (Table 1) are in agreement with the proposed formulation of the complexes as Cd(ald-aa).3H₂O (where, ald = sal/OHN and aa = gly, L-ala, L-phen, L-val, L-leu, L-his and L-try). The metal complexes are solid, non-hygroscopic and insoluble in almost all common organic solvents except DMF, DMSO and acetic acid. The molar conductance values of the complexes (10⁻³ M in DMF) (Table 1) showed their non-electrolytic nature. The structures 1 and 2 have been

confirmed on the basis of ir, ¹H nmr, electronic spectra and conductivity measurements.

The infrared spectra of the complexes showed a broad band at 3400–3300 cm⁻¹ (OH) of water molecules. The intense and well-resolved band appearing around 1630 cm⁻¹ (N=CH) for all the complexes indicated the presence of imine structure. The observed ν(COO⁻) band was consistently > 200 cm⁻¹ [ν(COO⁻)_{as} ~ 1600 and ν(COO⁻)_{sym} ~ 1400 cm⁻¹] which indicated unidentate coordination by the carboxylic group⁴. The ν_{C-O} (phenolic) stretching was observed at 1540–1525 cm⁻¹ for all the complexes⁵. The two weaker bands at 800–750 and 720–700 cm⁻¹ were assigned as OH rocking and wagging vibrations respectively, of coordinated water in the complexes. Previous workers⁶ observed the last two bands at 900–650 cm⁻¹. Far-ir spectra of all the complexes showed medium intense broad bands at 520–480 (M–N)⁷ and 440–400 cm⁻¹ (M–O)⁸.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
	M	C	H	N	
Cd(sal-gly).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	32.32 (32.73)	31.11 31.45	1.94 2.04	3.87 4.08	11.71
Cd(sal-L-ala).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	31.09 (31.45)	33.25 33.58	2.60 2.52	3.66 3.92	10.36
Cd(sal-L-phen).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	25.58 (25.93)	44.12 44.30	3.01 3.00	2.98 3.23	18.36
Cd(sal-L-val).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	28.92 (29.16)	37.10 37.36	3.15 3.37	3.40 3.63	12.30
Cd(sal-L-leu).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	28.15 (28.14)	39.00 39.06	3.72 3.76	3.59 3.51	11.04
Cd(sal-L-his).3H ₂ O (Light yellow)	26.31 (26.55)	36.69 36.84	2.46 2.60	9.71 9.92	10.00
Cd(sal-L-try).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	23.55 (23.79)	45.37 45.72	3.03 2.96	5.78 5.93	13.24
Cd(OHN-gly).3H ₂ O (Light yellow)	28.37 (28.57)	39.30 39.65	2.11 2.29	3.33 3.56	11.66
Cd(OHN-L-ala).3H ₂ O (Light yellow)	27.27 (27.59)	41.00 41.24	2.38 2.70	3.22 3.44	11.35
Cd(OHN-L-Phen).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	23.09 (23.25)	49.31 49.65	2.97 3.10	2.65 2.90	20.00
Cd(OHN-L-Val).3H ₂ O (Light yellow)	25.44 (25.82)	43.85 44.10	3.30 3.45	3.10 3.22	14.18
Cd(OHN-L-leu).3H ₂ O (Light yellow)	25.05 (25.01)	45.10 45.39	3.48 3.78	3.10 3.12	10.81
Cd(OHN-L-his).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	23.35 (23.74)	42.90 43.09	2.55 2.75	8.43 8.81	10.10
Cd(OHN-L-try).3H ₂ O (Colourless)	21.41 (21.52)	50.63 50.54	3.10 3.06	5.17 5.36	15.92

Uv spectra of the Cd^{II} complexes in DMF showed two absorption bands. The low energy absorption band near 350 nm was assigned to conjugated imine $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition originating mainly in the aldimine residue. At higher energies, the complexes exhibited intense absorption bands, with maxima near 260 nm, which may be attributed to benzenoid $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. Casella and Gullotti⁹ observed similar types of bands in the electronic spectra of zinc(II) complexes of salicylidene- and pyridoxylidamino-acid Schiff bases.

¹H nmr spectra of the Cd^{II} complexes were studied in TFA. The δ values (in ppm) are given in Table 2. The azomethine proton of Cd(sal-aa).3H₂O was observed at δ 8.0–8.80. Integration of the multiplet comprised between δ 6.80 and 8.00 accounted for four protons in the spectra of Cd(sal-gly).3H₂O, Cd(sal-L-ala).3H₂O, Cd(sal-L-val).3H₂O and Cd(sal-L-leu).3H₂O and nine protons in the spectra of Cd(sal-

L-try).3H₂O and Cd(sal-L-phen).3H₂O. For Cd(sal-L-his).3H₂O, five aromatic protons (including H_B) were observed as multiplet at δ 7.10–8.00, while H_A signal was observed at δ 8.65. The aliphatic protons present in the complex are shown in Table 2.

For Cd(OHN-aa).3H₂O, azomethine proton can be attributed to the signal at δ 8.50–9.50. Six protons at δ 7.15–8.50 for Cd(OHN-gly).3H₂O, Cd(OHN-L-ala).3H₂O, Cd(OHN-L-val).3H₂O and Cd(OHN-L-leu).3H₂O, and eleven protons for Cd(OHN-L-phen).3H₂O and Cd(OHN-L-try).3H₂O are accounted on the basis of integration of the multiplet. In case of Cd(OHN-L-his).3H₂O nine aromatic protons were observed at δ 7.48–8.65. The aliphatic protons present in the complexes are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—¹H NMR SPECTRA OF Cd^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	δ
Cd(sal-gly).3H ₂ O	4.78 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.05–7.80 (4H, m, ArH), 8.50 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(sal-L-ala).3H ₂ O	1.90 (3H, d, CH ₃), 3.10 (1H, q, α -CH), 7.05–8.00 (4H, m, ArH), 8.55 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(sal-L-phen).3H ₂ O	3.60 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.90 (1H, m, α -CH), 6.90–7.50 (9H, m, ArH), 8.00 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(sal-L-val).3H ₂ O	1.20 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.25 (3H, d, CH ₃), 2.65 (1H, m, CH(CH ₃) ₂), 4.70 (1H, d, α -CH), 7.10–8.00 (4H, m, ArH), 8.80 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(sal-L-leu).3H ₂ O	1.10 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.17 (3H, d, CH ₃), 2.20 (3H, m, (CH ₃) ₂ CH-CH ₂), 4.95 (1H, m, α -CH), 7.20–8.00 (4H, m, ArH), 8.66 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(sal-L-his).3H ₂ O(1)	3.85 (2H, d, CH ₂), 5.30 (1H, t, α -CH), 7.10–8.00 (5H, m, ArH including H _B), 8.65 (1H, s, H _A), 8.80 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(sal-L-try).3H ₂ O	3.64 (2H, d, CH ₂), 4.60 (1H, m, α -CH), 6.80–7.70 (9H, m, ArH), 8.20 (1H, m, azomethine proton)
Cd(OHN-gly).3H ₂ O	5.05 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.30–8.40 (6H, m, ArH), 9.50 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(OHN-L-ala).3H ₂ O	2.10 (3H, d, CH ₃), 5.25 (1H, q, α -CH), 7.40–8.50 (6H, m, ArH), 9.50 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(OHN-L-phen).3H ₂ O	3.80 (2H, d, CH ₂), 5.15 (1H, d, α -CH), 7.30–8.00 (11H, m, ArH), 8.50 (1H, s, azomethine proton)

Table-2 (Contd.)

Cd(OHN-L-val) 3H ₂ O(2)	1.30 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.39 (3H, d, CH ₃), 2.75 (1H, m, CH(CH ₃) ₂), 4.90 (1H, d, α-CH), 7.40-8.50 (6H, m, ArH), 9.50 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(OHN-L-leu).3H ₂ O	0.95 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.00 (3H, d, CH ₃), 2.05 (3H, m, (CH ₃) ₂ CH-CH ₂), 4.85 (1H, m, α-CH), 7.15-8.20 (6H, m, ArH), 9.30 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(OHN-L-his) 3H ₂ O	4.10 (2H, d, CH ₂), 5.58 (1H, m, α-CH), 7.48-8.65 (9H, m, ArH), 8.85 (1H, s, azomethine proton)
Cd(OHN-L-try).3H ₂ O	3.85 (2H, d, CH ₂), 5.00 (1H, m, CHCH ₂), 7.20-8.50 (11H, m, ArH), 9.30 (1H, s, azomethine proton)

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of AnalaR grade. Salicylaldehyde (Sarabhai M. Chemicals), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Sisco-Chem), amino acids (Loba-Chemie) and cadmium acetate (Albright and Wilson) were used. Metal contents were estimated using standard methods¹⁰.

Ir spectra of the metal complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 842 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a U-2000 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

To prepare the metal complexes, an aqueous solution of sodium salt of amino acids was treated with hot ethanolic solution of the aldehyde in equimolar ratio. The aqueous ethanolic solution of cadmium acetate was added to hot ligand solution in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The reactants were stirred for about 15 h. The products, so formed, were filtered, washed with water-ethanol mixture and finally with

diethyl ether. The samples were dried under reduced pressure over P₂O₅. The purity was checked by tlc. The yield of the complexes varied between 80 and 90%.

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